

LEARNING STYLES IN MODULAR DISTANCE LEARNING AND THE ENGLISH ACHIEVEMENT OF GRADE V PUPILS

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ABSTRACT

Change in education brought by the pandemic situation is indeed quite a challenge for the learners especially the educators. The use of Modular Distance Learning in delivering the lessons or topics clearly to the learners is widely used especially in areas where online platform is not suitable. This study focused in determining the relationship between the Learning Styles and English achievement of Grade V pupils using the MDL. This study is a descriptive -correlational kind of research in which it uses a survey questionnaire from a standardized VAK Learning Style Questionnaire and a modified-adopted English test. There were sixty-one Grade V respondents from two chosen public elementary schools of Dolores District, Division of Quezon where the researcher taught and was also conducted last March, 2021. Based on the result of the perceived learning style of the respondents, most of the respondents are visual type of learner as compared to auditory/aural and kinesthetic/tactile style. The result of their English test falls under proficient level where it clearly indicates that whether the respondents is visual, aural or kinesthetic style of learner, they are still proficient in English in terms of reading comprehension, vocabulary and grammar. The visual learning style showed significant relationship between the English achievement in terms of reading comprehension, vocabulary and grammar. However, in terms of auditory/aural learning style, only vocabulary found to be significantly related. In spite of this result, as for the recommendations, teachers and/or educators must be aware on the learning style preference of their students to provide activities, topics or discussions that would suits best to the learning style needed by the learners and must be creative and resourceful in crafting learning materials that would be distributed to learners. Be mindful on their preferred learning style to help them improve their academic course and the future researchers may conduct similar or more complex study in line with this.

Keywords: visual learning styles, auditory/aural learning styles, kinaesthetic/tactile learning styles, English achievement